

Epidemiological Overview of Inguinal Herniorrhaphies in Brazil

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Abstract

Introduction: Inguinal hernia is one of the most prevalent surgical conditions, characterized by the protrusion of abdominal viscera through the inguinal canal, predominantly affecting men. Its etiology involves congenital or acquired weakness of the abdominal wall, aggravated by increased intra-abdominal pressure. Despite advances in videolaparoscopic techniques, open herniorrhaphy remains predominant in the Unified Health System (SUS). This study aims to analyze the epidemiological panorama of inguinal herniorrhaphy in Brazil between 2008 and 2024. Materials and Methods: Ecological, cross-sectional, and descriptive study with secondary data from the Hospital Information System (SIH/SUS). Variables evaluated included number of hospitalizations, mortality, average length of stay, type of procedure (open or laparoscopic), elective or emergency nature, costs, and demographic profile stratified by macroregions, with calculation of the prevalence ratio (PR) according to age, sex, and race/ethnicity. Results: A total of 2,331,173 procedures were recorded, of which 2,315,088 were open and 16,085 were laparoscopic. Mortality was low (0.1% for open and 0.15% for laparoscopic), but significantly higher in emergencies. The age distribution was bimodal, with peaks at 0–4 years (PR=1.6) and 60–79 years (up to PR=2.21). Males accounted for 84% of cases (PR=1.73), and the brown population had a higher relative prevalence (PR=2.95). The Southeast concentrated the highest volume and total expenditure, while the North had higher mortality and mean hospital stay. The open approach generated a higher accumulated cost (US\$261 million) compared to laparoscopic (US\$1.38 million). Discussion/Conclusion: Open herniorrhaphy remains predominant in Brazil, although videolaparoscopy shows gradual growth and equivalent safety. The findings highlight regional inequalities and reinforce the need for investment in minimally invasive techniques, infrastructure, and equity in access to improve outcomes and optimize resources.

Keywords: herniorrhaphies, inguinal, surgery.

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Introduction

Inguinal hernias are one of the most prevalent conditions among surgical emergencies, characterized by the protrusion of abdominal viscera (usually loops of the small intestine) through the inguinal canal. This occurs primarily due to defects in the integrity of the abdominal wall. These conditions account for approximately 75% of all abdominal wall hernias and predominantly affect males, with an estimated 9:1 ratio compared to females.

The pathophysiology involves a combination of inguinal muscle weakness and increased intra-abdominal pressure (IAP). This structural defect can be congenital or acquired and is influenced by genetic factors, alterations in tissue structure, and collagenopathies such as an imbalance between type I and type III collagen. Aging, in turn, also contributes to tissue degeneration, increasing the susceptibility to potential hernia protrusions [4].

An inguinal hernia usually presents as a swelling in the groin area, which may be asymptomatic or not and is frequently exacerbated by physical exertion, coughing, or the Valsalva maneuver. In untreated cases, there is a risk of complications, including hernia incarceration and strangulation, the latter being a surgical emergency with the potential to progress to necrosis, peritonitis, and sepsis. 4 Risk factors contribute to the development of the disease, such as advanced age, male gender, smoking, obesity, family history, and conditions that increase IAP, such as ascites or intense physical exertion [4].

Treatment is exclusively surgical and includes both open techniques, such as Lichtenstein herniorrhaphy with polypropylene mesh, and minimally invasive approaches, such as laparoscopic TAPP and TEP repairs [5,6]. Laparoscopic procedures offer advantages such as less postoperative pain and faster recovery, although they require more extensive hospital infrastructure and specialized training [7,8].

In Brazil, this condition is among the main indications for abdominal surgery in the Unified Health System (SUS). Proof of this is that between 2013 and 2022, more than 1.3 million cases were diagnosed, with a male predominance (85%) and a higher incidence in the 60-69 age group.

This study aims to present the epidemiological profile of these procedures in Brazil and their social, economic, and public health implications.

Materials and Methods

This is an ecological, cross-sectional, and descriptive study aimed to analyze inguinal hernia repairs in Brazil between 2008 and 2024, by place of residence, according to chapter K40 of ICD-10: Inguinal Hernia. Data were obtained secondary through the Hospital Information System (SIH/SUS), available on the platform of the SUS Information Technology Department (DATASUS), of the Brazilian Ministry of Health. The records included both elective and emergency admissions, covering all age groups and genders. The search terms used were: "INGUINAL / CRURAL HERNIOPLASTY (UNILATERAL)", "INGUINAL HERNIOPLASTY (BILATERAL)", "VIDEOLAPAROSCOPIC INGUINAL HERNIORRHAPHY".

The variables analyzed included: approved hospital admission authorizations (AIH), total amount spent, average length of stay in days, deaths, mortality rate, type of care, and epidemiological characteristics (sex, age group, and race/ethnicity). Furthermore, the data were broken down by Brazilian macroregions: North, Northeast, Southeast, South, and Central-West.

To calculate the cost in dollars, the exchange rate of July 4, 2024, was used, at 5.4084, according to the Central Bank of Brazil.

The TABNET tool was used for data extraction, with export in CSV format. The data were tabulated, organized, and analyzed using Microsoft® Excel® (version 2506). The information was presented using line and column graphs, absolute and relative frequency tables, and mean values, allowing for comparative analysis between the different regions over the study period.

To better understand the temporal evolution of the presented variables, line graphs were constructed for the period between 2008 and 2024, accompanied by linear trend lines (simple linear regression).

The prevalence ratio (PR) was used as a measure of association to compare the probability of inguinal hernia occurrence among different population strata, considering the variables: age group, sex, and race/ethnicity. The calculation was based on the ratio between the proportion of cases observed in the exposed group and the proportion of the same group in the general population. The population estimates required for standardizing the proportions were obtained from the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) in 2022. This

approach allowed us to identify which subgroups presented a higher or lower relative risk for the condition analyzed throughout the study period.

It is noteworthy that this study, because it uses public domain data with unrestricted access, does not require submission to the Research Ethics Committee, in accordance with Resolution No. 510 of April 7, 2016, of the National Health Council.

Results

From 2008 to 2024, 2,315,088 open inguinal hernioplasties (OIH) and 16,085 videolaparoscopic inguinal herniorrhaphies (VILH) were recorded in Brazil.

The data collected indicate an absolute number of deaths of 2,274 for OIH and 25 for VILH. Regarding the mortality rate, it was 0.1 and 0.15 for IAH and HIV, respectively.

In a temporal analysis, the number of procedures using the conventional approach remained constant over the years, with a slight downward trend, while the laparoscopic approach showed a slight upward trend. It is noteworthy that for both procedures, 2020 and 2021 represented a significant decrease, followed by a peak in 2022, 2023, and 2024.

Regarding the nature of the care, 80% of IAH procedures were elective and 20% were urgent, while approximately 71% of HIV were elective and 29% were urgent.

Regarding the total costs, these show a downward trend, with IAH representing a cost of \$261,825,846.50 and HIV, \$1,386,181, over the years.

Another variable analyzed was the average length of stay, which proved to be stable, with no significant fluctuations over the years.

In the analysis by age group (Figure 1), it was observed that inguinal hernias presented a bimodal distribution in absolute numbers, with peaks in the 0-4 age group (261,754 cases) and 60-69 age group (440,981 cases). Regarding the relative risk (RR), the 0-4 age group had an RR of 1.6. The subsequent age groups, from 5 to 49 years, demonstrated a protective effect, with RR ranging from 0.2 to 0.9. In the 50-59 age group, the risk increased again, with an RR of 1.49, followed by the 60-69 age group, which had an RR of 2.0. The highest risk was observed among individuals aged 70 to 79, with a RR of 2.21, with a reduction in the group aged 80 or over, whose RR was 1.16.

In the regional analysis (Figure 1), the age distribution followed the general trend across all regions. The states with the highest number of inguinal hernia patients were the Southeast, with 962,197 cases, followed by the Northeast with 733,115, which together account for more than half of the national records. The South, North, and Central-West regions had smaller volumes, with 404,578, 211,134, and 173,817 cases, respectively.

Figure 1: Distribution of Approved Hospital Admission Authorizations (AIH) for Inguinal Hernia Repair by Age Group and Region in Brazil (2008–2024)

Regarding the gender distribution, males were overwhelmingly predominant, with 2,093,239 cases, approximately 84% of cases, while females accounted for 391,602 cases. In the RR survey, males had a protective factor of 1.73, while females had a protective factor of 0.3. The regional analysis demonstrated the same proportions as the national scenario for all regions.

In the epidemiological analysis, incidence was also investigated by race/ethnicity, with brown being the most prevalent, with 963,095 cases. In absolute numbers, white people followed with 824,595, black people with 80,356, Asian people with 30,429, and indigenous people with 2,497. Regarding the RR, with the exception of brown people (with an RR of 2.95), all other race/ethnicity groups had an RR below 1, ranging from 0.16 to 0.85.

In the analysis by approved AIH, the region with the highest number of hospitalizations due to IAH was the Southeast with 868,497 procedures, followed by the Northeast with 696,019, the South with 383,977, the North with 203,945, and the Midwest with 162,650.

Regarding HIVL procedures, the Southeast region maintained its position as the region with the highest number of procedures (5,724 procedures). However, the South now occupies second place, with 4,470 procedures, followed by the Northeast with 2,556, the North with 1,676, and the Central-West with 1,659.

When analyzing only HIVL procedures performed as emergencies, the North region stands out with 945 procedures (even surpassing the number of elective procedures performed in the same region - 731 procedures), trailing only the Southeast (1,319).

The year with the highest number of elective procedures performed using the open and laparoscopic approaches was 2024, with 168,885 and 1,320, respectively (Figure 2). Contrary to the general upward trend, the year with the lowest number of elective procedures in the entire time series was 2020, with only 56,117 open herniorrhaphies and 418 laparoscopic approaches (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Distribution of Approved Hospital Admissions (AIH) for Elective Herniorrhaphy by Region in Brazil (2008–2024)

Also noteworthy is the decreasing trend in the number of open procedures performed on an emergency basis. In the longitudinal analysis, the peak number began in 2008, with 46,117 open procedures and 320 laparoscopic procedures. By the end of 2024, the number of open procedures reached less than half, with 19,965, and the equivalent number of laparoscopic procedures (315 procedures). From a broad perspective, both open and laparoscopic approaches demonstrated the same pattern of decline in 2020 and 2021, followed by increases in 2022, 2023, and 2024. Regarding deaths, open inguinal hernioplasty recorded 2,274 deaths in the analyzed period, corresponding to a mortality rate of 0.1%. Meanwhile, laparoscopic inguinal herniorrhaphy resulted in 25 deaths, with a proportionally similar rate of 0.15%. When comparing mortality rates according to the type of care (Figure 3), it was found that procedures performed as emergency procedures had significantly higher mortality in both approaches. In open hernioplasty, the overall mortality rate was 0.03%

in elective procedures, rising to 0.38% in emergency procedures—more than ten times higher. For the laparoscopic approach, the rate was 0.07% in elective cases and 0.37% in emergency cases. The region with the highest mortality rate for the open approach was the Southeast, at 0.11%, while for the laparoscopic approach, it was the North, at 0.35%. It is also noteworthy that the North Region had the highest mortality rates in elective procedures for both techniques: 0.04% for open surgery and 0.27% for laparoscopic surgery.

Figure 3: Distribution of Herniorrhaphy Mortality Rate by Type of Admission (Elective vs. Emergency) and Region in Brazil (2008–2024)

The Southeast Region had the highest cumulative expenditure, totaling approximately US\$100,885,576. Next, the Northeast (\$75,060,331), South (\$47,090,931), North (\$21,490,310), and Central-West (\$17,298,696) regions stand out. Regarding the videolaparoscopic approach, the Southeast Region also concentrated the largest amount of resources applied, with US\$551,687, followed by the South (\$367,557), Northeast (\$198,367), North (\$139,417), and Central-West (\$129,152).

Regarding the average hospital stay, the data analyzed indicate that, throughout the period evaluated, patients undergoing open inguinal hernioplasty remained, on average, 1.5 days in hospital for elective procedures and 2.3 days for emergency procedures. Similarly, patients undergoing laparoscopic inguinal herniorrhaphy had an average hospital stay of 1.5 days for elective procedures and 2.5 days for emergency procedures. The North Region, once again, stood out negatively, recording the longest average hospital stays for both surgical approaches, reaching 2.1 days for both open and laparoscopic procedures, which may reflect differences in access, hospital infrastructure, or the severity of the cases treated in this region.

Discussion

The analysis of hospital data on inguinal hernia admissions between 2008 and 2024 in Brazil revealed important information about the epidemiological, healthcare, and financial performance of open surgical procedures compared to laparoscopic procedures. The significant discrepancy in the number of procedures performed between the two techniques—more than 2.3 million open hernioplasties versus just over 16,000 laparoscopic procedures—highlights the consolidation of the open approach as the standard in the SUS (Unified Health System), possibly due to factors such as lower technical complexity, greater availability of trained professionals, and hospital infrastructure compatible with this type of procedure [10].

Despite the predominance of the open technique, there is a gradual, albeit still modest, trend toward increasing videolaparoscopy. This growth may reflect technological advancements, the progressive training of healthcare professionals, and the incorporation of

international guidelines that highlight the benefits of the minimally invasive technique, such as reduced postoperative pain and faster recovery, especially in referral centers. The bimodal distribution by age group—with peaks among children aged 0 to 4 years and older adults aged 60 to 79 years—reinforces the congenital nature of hernias in childhood and the degenerative nature of senescence, as indicated in previous studies [11]. The increasing relative risk from age 50 onward, culminating in the 70 to 79 age group, emphasizes the need for clinical surveillance in this population, given their greater vulnerability and possible associated comorbidities.

The male predominance (84% of cases) is consistent with national and international literature, as male anatomy favors the formation of inguinal hernias [12]. The high prevalence ratio among men (RR = 1.73) reinforces this biological association. Regarding the race/color variable, the highest prevalence among mixed-race individuals stands out, followed by white and black individuals, which may reflect not only genetic factors but also social inequalities and in access to healthcare [13]. Regionally, the Southeast region accounted for the largest number of procedures and the highest expenditures, consistent with its demographic weight and concentration of healthcare resources. However, the North region stands out negatively, with higher mortality rates, longer average hospital stays, and a high number of emergency procedures—indicators that may reflect barriers to early access to care and structural limitations.

The mortality analysis revealed a higher risk in emergency procedures, regardless of the surgical approach. This finding is consistent with the literature, which links emergency surgeries to worse clinical outcomes.

The proportionally similar mortality rate between the approaches (0.1% for open and 0.15% for laparoscopic) suggests that the minimally invasive approach, although newer, is safe when appropriately indicated.

The cost associated with open hernioplasties was substantially higher than that of laparoscopic hernioplasties, in part due to the greater volume of procedures. However, this analysis does not allow us to conclude whether videolaparoscopy would be more cost-effective, as indirect costs such as recovery time, return to work, and complications were not included.

Conclusion

In Brazil, open inguinal hernioplasty remains the most widely used technique. The laparoscopic approach, although still a minority, is showing a growing trend and maintains mortality rates and average hospital stays similar to the conventional technique, indicating its viability and safety. The epidemiology of inguinal hernia in the country shows a greater impact among children and the elderly, with a predominance in males and a higher incidence in the mixed-race population. Regional inequalities are also observed, especially in the North Region, which highlight disparities in access to healthcare and reinforce the need for public policies focused on equity.

The results highlight the importance of expanding access to minimally invasive techniques through investments in professional training, improving hospital infrastructure, and promoting equity in the healthcare system. Future research that includes cost-effectiveness analyses and postoperative quality of life assessments could support more assertive decisions aligned with the Brazilian reality.

This study, while comprehensive, has inherent limitations to the use of secondary data from DATASUS, which do not allow for in-depth

analysis of specific patient clinical characteristics or long-term outcomes. For future research, prospective multicenter studies integrating detailed clinical data are recommended, allowing for analyses adjusted for comorbidities and disease severity.

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